

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Diphenyl Sulfoxide by Sodium N-Chloro 4-Methyl Benzene Sulfonamide in Presence of Hydrochloric Acid

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The kinetics of oxidation of diphenyl sulfoxide (DPSO) by sodium N-chloro 4-methyl benzene sulfonamide or chloramine-T (CAT) is studied at 40° in HCl medium. The product is diphenyl sulfone. The rate law is found to be, $-d[\text{CAT}]/dt = k[\text{CAT}][\text{H}^+]$. Ionic strength of the medium and addition of *p*-toluene sulfonamide have no effect, but chloride ion catalyses the reaction, showing that the rate law is of the form :

$$-d[\text{CAT}]/dt = k_1[\text{CAT}][\text{H}^+] + k_2[\text{CAT}][\text{Cl}^-]^{0.8}$$

The observed rate law is interpreted in terms of a fast interaction between DPSO and H_2OCl^+ formed from the hydrolysis of N-chloro *p*-toluene sulfonamide in a slow step or from the hydrolysis of Cl_2 formed from the free acid and added Cl^- ion.

MECHANISMS of many oxidation reactions of sodium N-chloro-4-methyl benzene sulfonamide, $p\text{-CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NCINa}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ commonly called chloramine-T (CAT) have been kinetically investigated¹⁻¹⁵. This reagent can oxidise compounds containing S-O bonds to the respective sulfones¹⁶. We have reported on the kinetics of oxidation of dimethyl sulfoxide by CAT in aqueous solution¹⁷. Studies on a mixed sulfoxide, namely, phenyl methyl sulfoxide have been made recently¹⁸. It was found worthwhile to study the oxidation of diphenyl sulfoxide (DPSO) by CAT in presence of HCl (0.04-0.08M). It may be mentioned that kinetic investigations on the oxidation of an aromatic sulfoxide by CAT have not been reported in literature.

Experimental

Diphenyl sulfoxide (Fluka AG) was used without further purification. A solution of the compound was prepared in ethanol water (50 : 50, v/v) mixture. Other experimental details are similar to those described in the previous communication¹⁷. The reaction was sluggish in acid medium at 0°. Hence all rate studies were made at 40°. Pseudo first order conditions were maintained and the kinetics were followed nearly to three half lives. The first order rate constants evaluated by the graphical method were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometry :

Reaction mixtures containing excess CAT over

DPSO were kept at room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$) in presence of 0.04–0.08 M HCl for 24 hours. Estimation of the unreacted CAT showed that one mole of DPSO consumed one mole of CAT.

The sulfonamide was identified by paper chromatography. Benzyl alcohol saturated with water was used as the solvent with 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ether as the spray reagent ($R_F = 0.905$). Presence of diphenyl sulfone was detected by the tlc technique. A mixture of petroleum ether (60-80°) chloroform and butanol (1 : 1 : 1, v/v) was the solvent and concentrated H_2SO_4 was used as the spray reagent ($R_F = 0.52$).

Results

At constant $[\text{H}^+]$, with the substrate in large excess, plots of $\log[\text{CAT}]$ vs time are linear indicating first order dependence of rate on $[\text{CAT}]$ (Fig. 1). The pseudo first order rate constants k_1 are unaffected by an increase in substrate concentration (Table 1). Hence the rate is independent of DPSO. The reaction is acid catalysed and at constant $[\text{Cl}^-]$, shows a first order dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 2). A plot of $\log k_1$ vs. $\log[\text{H}^+]$ gives a straight line slope 0.98. At constant $[\text{H}^+]$, addition of Cl^- in the form of NaCl (Table-3) increases the rate and a plot $\log k_1$ vs $\log[\text{Cl}^-]$ gives a straight line of slope 0.80. When the catalysis is effected simultaneously by H^+ and Cl^- , an order of 1.8 on the gross concentration of HCl is observed, indicating

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that two different mechanistic pathways are involved,

Fig. 1. Plots of log (a-x) vs time for the oxidation of DPSO by CAT. [HCl]=0.1 M; [DPSO]=0.1 M; $\mu=0.5 M$; Temp.: 40°C, [CAT]=0.004 M (a), 0.005 M (b), 0.006 M (c), 0.007 M (d), 0.008 M (e), [EtOH]=35%.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANT CONCENTRATION ON REACTION RATE AT 40°C

[H ⁺]=0.04M 10 ³ [CAT] ₀ M	[EtOH]=35% [DPSO] ₀ M	$\mu=0.5M$ 10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹
4.0	0.10	8.48
5.0	0.10	8.49
6.0	0.10	8.41
7.0	0.10	8.38
8.0	0.10	8.38
5.0	0.15	8.34
5.0	0.20	8.40
5.0	0.25	8.36
5.0	0.30	8.37

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION ON REACTION RATE AT 40°C

[CAT]₀=0.005M; [DPSO]₀=0.1M; [EtOH]=35%; [Cl⁻]=0.08M; $\mu=0.5M$.

10 ² [H ⁺]M	10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹	10 ² k ₁ /[H ⁺]
4.0	14.75	36.87
5.0	18.19	36.37
6.0	22.49	37.47
7.0	25.83	36.90
8.0	29.20	36.50

Effect of varying the Dielectric constant :

The first order rate constant k₁ was affected by variation of ethanol in the ethanol-water content of the reaction mixture. With [ethanol]=30.0, 35.0, 40.0, 48.0, 55.0 and 60%, 10⁴k₁ sec⁻¹ values were 8.86, 8.49, 8.13, 7.45, 6.81 and 6.36 respectively. A plot of log k₁ vs 1/D (dielectric constant values were taken from literature^{19,20}) gives a straight line with a negative slope (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Plot of log k_{obs} vs 1/D for the oxidation of DPSO by CAT in presence of HCl. [HCl]=0.1 M; [DPSO]=0.1 M; $\mu=0.5 M$; Temp.: 40°C [CAT]=0.005M.

Effect of Neutral salts :

Increase in ionic strength of the medium from 0.5 to 0.8 using NaClO₄ affected k₁ only marginally (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH AND TOTAL CHLORIDE ION CONCENTRATION ON REACTION RATE AT 40°C

[CAT]₀=0.005M; [DPSO]₀=0.1M; [H⁺]=0.04M; [EtOH]=35%

[NaClO ₄]	10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹	10 ² [Cl ⁻]M	10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹
0.5	2.99	5.0	10.04
0.6	3.24	5.5	11.07
0.8	3.40	6.0	11.72
		7.0	13.41
		8.0	14.75

Effect of p-toluene Sulfonamide :

Addition of p-toluene sulfonamide (TSA) had negligible effect on the rate. With 10²[TSA]=0.0,

5.0, 10.0 and 20.0, values of $10^4 k_1$ were 8.4, 8.3, 8.2 and 8.2 sec^{-1} .

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON REACTION RATE

Temperature °k $10^4 k_1 \text{sec}^{-1}$	313.0 8.49	318.0 11.51	323.0 16.88	328.0 21.14
[CAT] ₀ =0.005M; [DPSO] ₀ =0.1M; [H ⁺]=0.04M; $\mu=0.5M$; [EtOH] ₀ =35%				

Effect of Temperature :

Kinetic runs were made at different temperatures (Table 4) and the activation parameters have been evaluated: $E_a = 52.3 \text{ kJ mole}^{-1}$; $\Delta H^\ddagger = 48.96 \text{ kJ mole}^{-1}$; $\Delta S^\ddagger = -147.4 \text{ JK}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 95.0 \text{ kJ mole}^{-1}$.

Evaluation of parameters under conditions, [CAT]= $6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; [DPSO]=0.15M; [HCl]=0.020M; [EtOH]=35% also gave identical results.

Fig. 3. Plot of $[H^+]/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[Cl^-]$ for the oxidation of DPSO by CAT in presence of HCl. [HCl]=0.1 M; [DPSO]=0.1 M; $\mu=0.5 M$; Temp.: 40°C [CAT]=0.005 M. [EtOH]=35%.

Discussion

The rate of oxidation of DPSO by CAT depends on [CAT] and $[H^+]$. This is in contrast to our observations with the oxidation of dimethyl sulfide¹⁷ by CAT, where in addition, a first order dependence of rate on the substrate concentration was noted. Introduction of the phenyl group probably increases the electron density at the hetero atom facilitating electrophilic attack by the positive halogen of oxidant¹⁸.

Protonation of DPSO is of little importance at low acidities as shown by Oae *et al.*²¹. On the other hand, protonation of CAT has been thoroughly investigated by Morris *et al.*²² and Higuchi and co-workers²³. Chloramine-T ionizes in aqueous solution as²⁴ :

The anion picks up a proton in acid solution to give the free acid RNHCl. The acid can undergo disproportionation and/or hydrolysis producing dichloramine-T (RNCl_2) and HOCl. Thus the probable oxidizing species in acidified CAT solutions are RNCl_2 , RNHCl and HOCl. If RNCl_2 were to be the reactive species, a second order dependence of rate on CAT is predicted from equation (1), which is contrary to the present experimental observations :

With RNHCl or HOCl, Schemes-I and II can be proposed for the oxidation of DPSO by CAT.

SCHEME-I

SCHEME-II

Scheme-I envisages the direct participation of RNHCl in a rate determining step. With the steady state approximation for RNHCl and assuming $k_2[S] > k_{-1}$, the rate law,

$$\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{CAT}][\text{H}^+] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

in agreement with experimental results can be derived. In Scheme-II, formation of HOCl takes place in a slow step through the hydrolysis of RNHCl, and is followed by a rapid protonation and reaction with the substrate. Rate law (2) can be derived by invoking steady state conditions for the intermediates and assuming $k_1[\text{CAT}][\text{H}^+] \gg k_{-2}[\text{RNH}_2][\text{HOCl}]$.

First approximation calculations by Bishop and Jennings²⁴ on decinormal solutions of CAT have shown that concentrations of RNHCl and HOCl are approximately 10^{-2} and $10^{-7}M$ respectively, around pH 0.1. Although the concentration of former species is larger, Pryde and Soper²⁵ have shown that interaction of RNHCl with the substrates could be slow, while HOCl would attack at a faster rate. Protonation converts the latter into a stronger electrophile than the precursor RNHCl, and it can attack the sulfoxide at a faster rate. Absence of significant ionic strength effect on the rate rules out the involvement of ions in a rate determining step (i.e., Scheme-I). Further, a change in the solvent composition by varying the ethanol content in ethanol-water affects the reaction rate. The general equation relating to the effect of dielectric constant D to the reaction velocity in a bimolecular reaction has been derived by Landskroener and Laidler²⁶. For the limiting case of zero angle of approach between two dipoles, Amis²⁷ has shown that

$$\ln k'_D = \ln k_D - 2\mu_1\mu_2/DkTr^3 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where k'_D is a function of dielectric constant D, μ_1 and μ_2 are the dipole moments of the reactants, r is the distance of approach for the two dipoles, k is the Boltzman constant and T is the absolute temperature. Equation (3) predicts a linear relation between $\log k_{obs}$ and $\frac{1}{D}$. The slope of the line should be negative for a reaction between two dipolar molecules, while a positive slope is obtained for ion-dipole reactions. In the present investigations, the plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\frac{1}{D}$ is linear with a negative slope, thus supporting the participation of two dipolar species in Step (ii) of Scheme-II.

A detailed mechanism of oxidation of DPSO by CAT in acid medium is shown in Scheme-III.

SCHEME-III

In Scheme-III, an electrophilic attack by the positive chlorine of H_2OCl^+ at the sulphur atom in the substrate is envisaged. A considerable degree of nucleophilicity is expected at this site because of the extended electron density due to $p\pi-d\pi$ overlap in the S—O bond and the presence of two phenyl rings in the molecule. The reaction intermediate formed in Step (I) hydrolyses through a fast step.

Values of the energy of activation and ΔS^\ddagger are comparable with those obtained during the oxidation of conjugated alcohols¹⁰, with CAT, where similar kinetics have been observed. The activation parameters are probably related to the protonation equilibria and the subsequent hydrolysis step (Scheme-II). Protonation of RNCl^- ion converts a more or less linear structure into a pyramidal arrangement and the sign of ΔS^\ddagger confirms the formation of such a compact structure.

Effect of Chloride ion :

The rate increases in presence of added chloride ion (Table 3) though a fractional order dependence (0.80) on the $[\text{Cl}^-]$ is seen. Such behaviour has been noted in the Orton rearrangement²⁸ of organic haloamides. The attacking species under these conditions will be either molecular chlorine formed by the interaction of RNHCl and Cl^- ion or HOCl formed in the hydrolysis of the former species. The observed kinetic behaviour can be explained by Scheme-IV.

SCHEME IV

Applying steady state conditions for RNHCl, it can be shown that

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{CAT}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]}{k_{-1} + k_2 [\text{Cl}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Under conditions $k_{-1} \gg k_2 [\text{Cl}^-]$, the rate expression becomes

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1}} [\text{CAT}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-] \quad \dots (5)$$

indicating a first order dependence of the rate in $[\text{Cl}^-]$. If $k_{-1} \ll k_2 [\text{Cl}^-]$, the rate expression becomes

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{CAT}] [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots (6)$$

The rate becomes independent of the chloride ion concentration. However, if $k_{-1} \approx k_2 [\text{Cl}^-]$, the order becomes fractional with respect to $[\text{Cl}^-]$, i.e., 0.8, in this case, as observed experimentally which is similar to Euler's case I(c)²⁹.

Equation (4) can be transformed into (7) and (8)

$$k_{\text{obs}} [\text{CAT}] = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{CAT}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]}{k_1 + k_2 [\text{Cl}^-]} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2 [\text{Cl}^-]} + \frac{1}{k_1} \quad \dots (8)$$

A plot of $[\text{H}^+]/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$ gives a straight line (Fig. 3). If $K = k_1/k_{-1} = 2.8 \times 10^{-5}$ at 25° (Morris *et al*²²), from the slope and intercept of the line, $k_2 = 1.64 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $k_{-1} = 5.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ sec}^{-1}$.

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